

Research on The Impact of E-Logistics Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction in E-Commerce

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study is to explore and identify the factors of e-logistics service quality that affect e-commerce customer satisfaction, thereby influencing customer loyalty. A survey was conducted to collect data from 187 young customers residing in Bac Tu Liem District, Hanoi. The collected data were analyzed using SPSS 20 and AMOS 20 to test the proposed hypotheses. A measuring instrument was used with six dimensions, that is, information quality, order fulfillment, customer service, service personalization, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. The results revealed that information quality, customer service, and service personalization all positively influence customer satisfaction. In contrast, order fulfillment was found to have no statistically significant impact on satisfaction. Furthermore, the study confirmed that customer satisfaction has a direct and strong effect on customer loyalty. Based on these findings, it is recommended that service providers implement a customer-centric strategy that ensures clear communication, responsive customer support, and tailored service experiences to better meet customer needs and expectations in the e-commerce environment.

Keywords: E-logistics, Customer Satisfaction, Customer Loyalty, Service Quality

1. Introduction

The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic has created profound changes in many socio-economic fields, especially in the strong development of e-commerce. The pandemic has not only promoted a strong shift from traditional to online shopping models but also created significant pressure on e-commerce businesses to optimize logistics processes. According to a report by the Ministry of Industry and Trade (2025), e-commerce in Vietnam accounts for two-thirds of the value of the digital economy and continues to grow strongly at a double-digit rate,

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reaching 18-25% per year. However, this means that e-commerce businesses face major logistics challenges, from improving delivery speed, optimizing costs, to ensuring customer service quality (Hasan Uvet, 2023). E-logistics has become a key factor to help e-commerce businesses maintain competitiveness and improve customer experience. e-logistics, with the integration of digital technology, not only helps optimize operational processes but also plays an important role in improving the quality of delivery services (e-commerce). According to Statista's report (2023), 54% of e-commerce businesses in Vietnam have difficulty in inventory control, which leads to out-of-stock or backlog of goods. These problems directly affect customer experience and the competitiveness of businesses in the increasingly fierce e-commerce market.

Currently, many international studies have focused on analyzing the role of e-logistics service quality in improving customer satisfaction in e-commerce, including studies by Nikunj Kumar Jain et al., (2021), Rao et al., (2011), Rashid & Rasheed, (2014). In Vietnam, although the e-commerce market is growing strongly, studies on the relationship between e-logistics service quality and customer satisfaction are still quite limited. Most of the current works only focus on traditional logistics services or general e-commerce, not fully exploiting the specific factors in e-logistics that directly affect customer experience. (Xiaofang Lin et al., 2023, Anchal Gupta et al., 2022). In particular, the connection between in-depth service factors and satisfaction has not been clearly studied, creating a gap that needs to be filled in the context of Vietnam. Based on that reality, this study was conducted to analyze in-depth e-logistics service quality factors and assess their impact on customer satisfaction in e-commerce, thereby contributing to the improvement of theory and practice in this field in Vietnam.

The main objective of this study is to analyze the impact of e-logistics service quality on customer satisfaction in the e-commerce sector in Vietnam. On that basis, the study aims to propose solutions to improve and enhance e-logistics service quality, contributing to optimizing operational processes and improving customer experience.

This study contributes to filling the theoretical gap on the impact of e-logistics service quality on customer satisfaction, especially in the context of Vietnam's e-commerce lacking in-depth studies on this topic. In practice, the study has important implications for e-commerce businesses by providing specific assessments of the impact of key factors in e-logistics such as information quality, customer service, service personalization and order fulfillment on customer satisfaction. The findings from the study will be a scientific basis for businesses to orient logistics process improvement, invest in management technology, and enhance training of customer service personnel, thereby increasing competitiveness and promoting sustainable development in the e-commerce environment.

2. Literature Review

2.1 constructs

2.1.1. E-logistics

“**E-logistics** refers to the impact of the Internet on supply chain processes – the process of planning, implementing, and controlling the efficient and effective flow and storage of goods, services, and related information – from the point of origin to the point of consumption, in order to meet customer requirements.” (Elkhateb, A., 2013). E-logistics is not only related to logistics activities such as transportation and storage of goods, but also includes order processing, optimizing returns, and providing value-added services to customers (Andreas Risberg, 2022; Angappa Gunasekaran et al., 2007). The goal of e-logistics is to reduce operating costs, meet delivery times, and improve customer service (Yu et al., 2016).

The development of e-commerce in recent years has promoted the strong development of e-logistics, expanding the market and applying new technologies such as Internet of Things (IoT), warehouse management system (WMS), and transportation management system (TMS), helping to optimize warehousing and transportation operations (Rashid & Rasheed, 2024) (N. Viswanadham & RS Gaonkar, 2001). E-logistics can be divided into B2B logistics (Business to Business) and B2C logistics (Business to Consumer), in which B2B logistics accounts for 80% of total operations, including inbound and outbound logistics, focusing on managing materials from suppliers to manufacturers, and from manufacturers to distributors (N. Viswanadham & RS Gaonkar, 2001). Meanwhile, B2C logistics mainly manages the delivery process from the manufacturer to the end consumer (Hasan Uvet, 2023). Modern e-logistics has become a core factor in the competitiveness of e-commerce businesses, helping to reduce costs and ensure the right order fulfillment (Hasan Uvet, 2023)

2.1.2 E-logistics service quality

In the field of e-logistics, service quality is defined as the extent to which logistics services meet or exceed customer expectations (X. Lin et al., 2023). Parasuraman et al. (1985) measured service quality through five basic dimensions: reliability, responsiveness, empathy, assurance, and tangibles. The rapid development of e-commerce has increased the importance of logistics and brought about many new challenges (Ying Yu et al., 2016). Retailers have to handle large and small orders, requiring fast delivery speed, high accuracy, and transparent information throughout the delivery process. Many studies have shown that the elements that constitute e-logistics services include information quality (Yen et al., 2022, Rashid & Rasheed, 2024), order fulfillment Croxton (2003), customer service (Rajendran et al., 2018), and service personalization (Ho & Bodoff, 2014, Ostrom et al. (2015).

Information quality in e-logistics is understood as the extent to which information meets the requirements of customers and organizations in the decision-making and operational processes. According to Choi et al. (2019), in online shopping, information quality refers to the simplicity

and accessibility in locating products and locations, while emphasizing the requirements of accuracy, timeliness, and convenience. Order fulfillment refers to product status, order accuracy, delivery timeliness, shipping costs, and product availability (Aamir Rashid & Rizwana Rasheed, 2024). Order fulfillment is a core process in supply chain management, involving the entire operation from customer order to product delivery. According to Arkadiusz Kawa (2017), order fulfillment includes receiving, storing, picking, packing, and shipping products, which are usually performed by an external operator to support the seller. Customer service is defined as tangible or intangible value-added activities, directly or indirectly related to a product or service, to meet the needs of the customer (Kursunluoglu, 2011). DH Nguyen (2016) adds that customer service occurs not only during the purchase but also before and after the purchase. Service Personalization in e-logistics is understood as the adjustment of products, services, or content based on the characteristics and needs of each customer instead of applying a uniform policy (Anand & Shachar, 2009). Personalization is also known as customization (Riemer et al., 2001). According to Fan, H. and Poole, MS (2006) personalization can be viewed as a three-dimensional implementation choice: what to personalize, who to personalize for, and who to personalize.

E-logistics service quality (E-LSQ) has a direct impact on customer satisfaction in e-commerce (Jain et al., 2021; Aamir Rashid & Rizwana Rasheed, 2024). Improving E-LSQ helps businesses not only retain customers but also increase competitiveness, reduce costs and increase operational efficiency in the increasingly competitive B2C market.

2.1.3 Customer satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is understood as a psychological state that reflects the comparison between previous expectations and the actual experience that customers receive (Oliver, 1997). According to Bailey et al. (1983), satisfaction includes the sum of users' feelings and attitudes towards the influencing factors during the use of a product or service. Some studies approach satisfaction from an emotional perspective (Anderson & Srinivasan, 2003), while others consider it a cognitive concept (Szymanski & Hise, 2000). In addition, Rao et al. (2011) also stated that satisfaction is the customer's emotional response when noticing the difference between expectations and actual performance of a product or service.

2.1.4 Customer loyalty

Loyalty is defined as an individual's attachment to an organization or the repeated use of a product or service of that organization (Omoregie et al., 2019). In the same view, (Shankar et al., 2004) also stated that customer loyalty is the fact that they continuously choose to use products or services from the same supplier, despite the presence of other alternatives in the market. Moreover, customers often prioritize choosing brands that they trust and have a good impression of (Yoo et al., 2000). When the need arises, they mainly consider familiar brands instead of looking for new options, showing a clear loyalty attitude towards the supplier (Gremler & Brown, 1996).

2.2 Hypothesis development

In e-commerce, where customers cannot directly contact the product, the role of information becomes even more important; businesses need to ensure that product information is provided fully and accurately to avoid confusion and loss of trust. According to (Rashid & Rasheed, 2024), to evaluate the quality of information, it can be based on three criteria: accurate product information, complete product information, and easy accessibility. In addition to product information, shipping information - including data on packaging time, warehouse, route and estimated delivery time - is also an essential component in e-logistics (Tran, 2022). The quality of shipping information helps ensure effective interaction between customers, sellers and shipping units, and supports the entire order fulfillment process. Information quality in e-logistics is not only a supporting factor but also a core foundation that determines customer satisfaction. According to research by (Tran, 2022), when customers receive transparent, accurate and real-time information, they can proactively track their orders, reduce uncertainty and increase trust in the service. An effective information system not only needs to be accurate and easy to understand, but also needs to be able to be continuously updated, helping customers make appropriate decisions throughout the shopping process. When information is unclear, misleading or delayed, customers may feel skeptical about the reliability of the service, leading to dissatisfaction and reduced satisfaction. In the same vein, research by (Yen et al., 2022, Rashid & Rasheed, 2024) also confirmed that information quality has a direct and significant impact on customer experience in e-logistics. Information quality, specifically the accuracy, completeness, timeliness, and accessibility of information related to orders and shipping, plays a key role in enhancing customer trust and satisfaction (Aamir Rashid & Rizwana Rasheed, 2024). Based on the above arguments, the authors propose the following research hypothesis:

“H1: Information quality has a positive influence on customer satisfaction.”

Order status is one of the most important factors affecting e-logistics service quality (Nikunj Kumar Jain, Hasmukh Gajjar & Bhavin J. Shah, 2021). Croxton (2003) emphasized that order fulfillment goes beyond delivery and involves designing networks and operational processes to meet customer requirements while optimizing total costs. Especially in the e-commerce environment, order fulfillment requires more specialized processes, including warehousing, order processing, packaging, shipping, and even website management and cloud-based order tracking (Claudia Isac, 2014). The order fulfillment in e-commerce process typically includes inventory management, last-mile delivery, and return processing (DH Nguyen, Leeuw & Dullaert, 2019). Efficient and effective operation of the order fulfillment process not only helps to meet customer needs quickly but also contributes to improving the overall shopping experience, increasing satisfaction and building competitive advantage for the business (Keely L. Croxton, 2003). A fast, accurate and friendly ordering process enhances the shopping experience, thereby increasing satisfaction and the likelihood of repurchase. (Hasan Uvet, 2023). Therefore, the study recommends the following:

“H2: Order fulfillment has a positive impact on customer satisfaction.”

An effective customer service not only helps customers access and purchase products but also helps businesses increase revenue, market share, profits and build a positive image in the market. From a logistics perspective, the focus is no longer just on reducing shipping costs but on providing added value to customers, through handling returns, customer support and customer relationship management (CJ Langley Jr & Mc Holcomb, 1992). In the context of e-commerce, where geographical distance is no longer a barrier, the requirements for customer service quality are increasingly high. Customers expect e-retailers to promptly resolve any questions or problems that arise related to orders, both before and after delivery (Jyoti Bhattacharjya et al., 2016). Customer service has a positive impact on customer satisfaction (Rajendran et al., 2018). Customer service not only meets immediate needs but also creates long-term value for the supply chain, when customer satisfaction becomes a source of sustainable value for the business. A well-organized customer service, taking care of customers at each stage of the product life cycle will contribute to creating competitive differences, while strengthening customer relationships in the current digital business environment. From the above analysis, this study proposes the hypothesis:

“H3: Customer service has a positive influence on customer satisfaction.”

Service Personalization, the ability to tailor delivery services to the individual needs of each customer, is increasingly gaining attention as a trend to enhance customer experience in e-logistics (Ricardo Guerrero. et al., (2020). According to Demirkan et al. (2015) and Peters et al. (2016), mining data from online behavior, purchase history, and customer feedback helps businesses build detailed customer profiles, thereby designing more suitable delivery services. This leads to a reduction in the gap between expectations and actual experiences, an important factor determining satisfaction (Ha et al., 2010). Many studies have shown that service personalization increases consumer satisfaction (Ho & Bodoff, 2014, Ostrom et al. (2015), Thomas et al. (2017), Moon et al. (2008). From an operations perspective, In service delivery, forms of personalization such as user-driven, system-driven, or real-time personalization all contribute to enhancing the customer experience by better meeting constantly changing needs (Instone, 2004; Treiblmaier et al., 2006). The ability of e-logistics systems to dynamically adapt, such as automatically suggesting changes to delivery schedules based on users' actual schedules, not only increases convenience but also strengthens customers' sense of control and satisfaction (Fan & Poole, 2006; Kim & Gambino, 2016). Empirical studies also show that when customers perceive contextually personalized service, they tend to be more loyal and rate service quality higher. Based on the above analysis, this study proposes the hypothesis:

“H4: Customer Personalization has a positive effect on customer satisfaction”.

Customer satisfaction has been identified as a key factor influencing loyalty. Studies have shown that satisfied customers are more likely to repeat purchases and maintain long-term relationships with brands than dissatisfied customers (Pleshko & Heiens, 2015; Devasagayam, 2012). Specifically, satisfaction strengthens the relationship between customers and businesses, thereby promoting loyalty (Omoregie et al., 2019). However, satisfaction does not completely

guarantee absolute loyalty, as there are still cases where customers are satisfied but not loyal due to influences from other brands (Fraering & Minor, 2013). However, many studies still confirm that satisfaction still plays an important role in forming loyalty (Tweneboah-Koduah & Farley 2015; Akamavi et al., 2015; Shen & Yahya, 2021). Oliver (1999) also suggested that repeated satisfaction can be transformed into strong loyalty, in addition, the study of Curry and Gao (2012) emphasized that satisfaction is a more effective predictor of re-use behavior than service quality. In short, satisfaction has a strong impact on customer loyalty, so the authors propose the hypothesis.

“H5: Satisfaction has a positive impact on customer loyalty”

Figure 1: Research Model

3. Methodology

3.1 Measurement model

In this study, the authors adopted a scale based on the scales of previous researchers who have studied the content related to this issue.

In which, the Information Quality (CL) scale is inherited from Dr.Aamir Rashid & Dr. Rizwana Rasheed (2024); Do Duc Anh. et al., (2023) including 5 observed variables, Order Fulfilment (DH) is inherited from the study of Sibel Akil & Mustafa Cahit Ungan (2022) including 5 observed variables, Customer Service (DV) is developed from the study of Tran Thi Thu Huong et al., (2024) including 5 observed variables, Service Personalization (CN) is built and

adjusted from the study of Ricardo Guerrero. et al., (2020), including 5 observed variables, Customer Satisfaction (HL) is referenced from the study of Vithya Leninkumar (2017) including 3 observed variables, and Customer Loyalty (TT) is inherited from Do Duc Anh et al. (2023); John Dickens et al., (2023) includes 3 observed variables.

3.2 Data

The respondents are young customers using e-commerce in the Bac Tu Liem, Hanoi. The research team collected data through a 5-level Likert questionnaire created on the Google Form platform. The sample was selected by a convenient, non-probability method with 187 valid survey samples, it can be affirmed that the sample size is sufficient to test the research hypotheses.

3.3 Data analysis /result

After collecting the survey questionnaires, the data were coded, cleaned and downloaded to SPSS 20 to analyze Cronbach's Alpha reliability and EFA exploratory factor. Then we used AMOS 20 software to analyze confirmatory factor analysis CFA and analyze linear structural model SEM to test discriminant validity, convergent validity, reliability and AVE to investigate and confirm the proposed hypothesis.

3.3.1 Statistical result

Table 1: Respondent Information

		Frequently	Percent (%)
Gender	Male	75	40.1
	Female	112	59.9
Age	18-25	135	72.2
	25-30	44	23.5
	30-35	7	3.7
	Above 35	1	0.5

Place	Minh Khai, Bac Tu Liem	52	27.8
	Phuc Dien, Bac Tu Liem	26	13.9
	Phu Dien, Bac Tu Liem	24	12.8
	Tay Tuu, Bac Tu Liem	29	15.5
	Xuan Dinh, Bac Tu Liem	13	7.0
	Other	43	23.0
Frequency	Very often	50	26.7
	Frequently	86	46.0
	Occasionally	42	22.5
	Rarely	7	3.7
	Never	2	1.1

3.3.2 Measurement model testing: Cronbach alpha, EFA, CFA

Table 2: Construct Reliability

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient
Product Quality	0.889
Order Fulfillment	0.873
Customer Service	0.885
Service Personalization	0.937
Customer Satisfaction	0.869
Customer Loyalty	0.879

The analysis results show that Cronbach's Alpha coefficients are all greater than 0.6, indicating good reliability. The Corrected Item-Total Correlation coefficients of all observed variables are > 0.3 . This shows that the observed variables all contribute to the overall reliability of the scale and are retained for use in the next factor analysis step.

Table 3: Results of KMO coefficient and Bartlett test for independent variables

KMO and Bartlett's Test		0.880
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	3485.877
	df	325
	Sig.	0.000

The results of factor analysis show that the KMO index is $0.880 > 0.5$, which proves that the data used for factor analysis is completely appropriate.

The Bartlett's test result is 1639.414 with a significance level (p value) $\text{sig} = 0.000 < 0.05$, so the variables are correlated with each other and satisfy the conditions for factor analysis.

Figure 2: Measurement Model

The results show that this model has a Chi-square/df value = $1.463 < 3$; RMSEA = $0.050 < 0.08$; CFI = $0.961 > 0.9$; TLI = $0.955 > 0.9$; GFI = $0.859 > 0.8$. Normally, the GFI index must be ≥ 0.9 , however, GFI is sensitive to sample size, so if $GFI > 0.8$, it is still valid. The Model Fit indexes are all valid, so this model is considered a model that fits well with the survey data set.

Table 4: Discriminant validity (Fornell-Larcker Criterion)

CR	AVE	MSV	MaxR(H)	CN	CL	DV	DH	HL	TT	
CN	0.937	0.748	0.312	0.961	0.865					
CL	0.882	0.600	0.176	0.891	0.304	0.775				
DV	0.886	0.608	0.437	0.888	0.538	0.306	0.780			
DH	0.887	0.615	0.076	0.922	0.119	0.275	0.257	0.784		
HL	0.870	0.690	0.464	0.871	0.494	0.376	0.642	0.206	0.831	
TT	0.879	0.708	0.464	0.882	0.559	0.420	0.661	0.248	0.681	0.841

The analysis results show that the influence of the variables is different. First, the greatest influence is the CN variable with a composite reliability of $CR = 0.937 > 0.7$. Second is the DH variable with a composite reliability of $CR = 0.887 > 0.7$. Third is the DV variable with a composite reliability of $CR = 0.886 > 0.7$. Fourth is the CL variable with $CR = 0.882 > 0.7$. Fifth is the TT variable with $CR = 0.879$. Finally, the HL variable with $CR = 0.870 > 0.7$. The extracted variance AVE of the 6 variables are all > 0.5 , confirming that the model has convergent value.

3.3.3 Hypothesis testing:

Figure 3: Structural Equation Modeling

The results of the SEM model analysis show that all indicators meet the criteria: Chi-square/df value = 1.549 < 3; RMSEA = 0.054 < 0.08; CFI = 0.953 > 0.9; TLI = 0.947 > 0.9; GFI = 0.848 > 0.8. Normally, the GFI indicator must be ≥ 0.9 , however, GFI is sensitive to sample size, so if GFI > 0.8, it is still valid. All indicators are reasonable, so this model is considered a good fit for the survey data set.

We ran the experiment with Bootstrapping sample size N = 2000 to evaluate the structural model.

Table 5: Hypothesis result

No.	Hypothesis	Regression path	Estimate	Sig.	Decision
1	H1	CL --> HL	.182	.010	Accepted
2	H2	DH --> HL	.021	.740	Rejected
3	H3	DV --> HL	.514	***	Accepted
4	H4	CN --> HL	.198	.009	Accepted
5	H5	HL --> TT	.734	***	Accepted
Note: *** = P < 0.001					

Except for the DH --> HL relationship which is not significant because p-value = 0.740 > 0.05, all other relationships are significant because p-value < 0.05. Therefore, H2 is rejected, H1, H3, H4, H5 are accepted. The regression coefficients of the relationships are all positive, so the relationships in the model are in the same direction.

4. Discussion and conclusion

The results of the research model analysis show that most of the hypotheses are accepted, except for hypothesis H2 (DH → HL) which is rejected due to lack of statistical significance (Sig = 0.740 > 0.05). Specifically, information quality (CL) has a positive impact on customer satisfaction with an estimated coefficient of 0.182 and a significance level of 0.010. This shows that providing accurate, complete, and reliable information plays an important role in increasing customer satisfaction, consistent with the results of Rashid and Rasheed (2024). Customer service (DV) shows the strongest influence on satisfaction (Estimate = 0.514, P < 0.001). This finding emphasizes the key role of customer care, including the ability to respond quickly, resolve complaints effectively, and maintain positive relationships with customers. This result reinforces the previous findings of Rajendran et al. (2018). In addition, service personalization (CN) also showed a positive impact on satisfaction (Estimate = 0.198, Sig = 0.009). Tailoring services to each customer’s individual needs enhances perceived value and engagement, consistent with the studies of Bodoff (2014), and Ostrom et al. (2015). Notably, customer satisfaction (HL) had a very strong influence on loyalty (TT) (Estimate = 0.734, P <

0.001), suggesting that enhancing satisfaction is the most effective way to retain customers in e-commerce. In contrast, order fulfillment (DH) is no longer a determinant of satisfaction in the modern customer environment, where they prioritize consistent service quality and personalized experiences over just completing orders on time, contrary to the research results of Mark Anthony Camilleri, (2021). This difference may reflect the change in expectations of modern consumers, where they want to get more value from the overall service and experience rather than just focusing on the speed of delivery.

This finding reinforces the argument that, in an increasingly competitive e-commerce environment, customer satisfaction is not only dependent on on-time delivery but is also strongly influenced by overall service quality (Keely L. Croxton, 2003) and the level of personalization of the experience (Instone, 2004; Treiblmaier et al., 2006). The fact that factors such as information quality (Rashid & Rasheed, 2024), customer service (Jyoti Bhattacharjya et al., 2016, Rajendran et al., 2018), and service personalization (Kim & Gambino, 2016) were found to have a significant impact suggests a shift in focus from operational efficiency to creating customer experience value (Ricardo Guerrero. et al., 2020). These findings highlight the need for innovative customer care strategies to enhance satisfaction and loyalty in the modern e-commerce market (Curry & Gao, 2012).

Contribution

This study has strengthened and expanded the theoretical basis of customer satisfaction and loyalty in the e-logistics sector in Vietnam. The results found that information quality, customer service and customer personalization have positive and significant impacts on customer satisfaction, while highlighting the strong mediating role of satisfaction on loyalty. In particular, this study has shown that the traditional order fulfillment factor no longer has an impact in the modern context, which explains that customers have a shift in priority from speed to experience quality. In terms of practice, the study provides important empirical evidence for e-logistics enterprises, especially prioritizing strategies to improve customer service, information quality and personalization of customer service experience. Recommendations from the research results help businesses optimize resources to improve customer satisfaction and loyalty, thereby enhancing competitive advantage in the context of the increasingly fierce e-commerce logistics market.

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